

INNOVATIVE TECHNOLOGIES IN LEARNING FOREIGN LANGUAGES

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<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.13338487>

ARTICLE INFO

Qabul qilindi: 30-iyul 2024 yil

Ma'qullandi: 9-avgust 2024 yil

Nashr qilindi: 15avgust 2024 yil

KEYWORDS

multimedia learning, paradigm learning, communicative activities, student intensification of independent work.

ABSTRACT

this article deals with the necessity and importance of innovative technology in the foreign language classroom. It also discusses in detail multimedia technology acting as a method for special intellectual activity. This technology has a number of advantages compared with other information technology training. The use of innovative learning technology creates the most favorable conditions and contributes significantly to motivation in learning foreign languages.

Learning foreign languages is impossible to imagine without the use of multimedia learning tools. Of course, important tasks for the methodology of teaching foreign languages include providing opportunities to illustrate the actual process of communication in English, and creating an educational environment that provides real conditions for learning use of the target language and its culture. The 21st century, often called the information age, is bringing about changes to the traditional teaching of language. The use of computer technology in teaching in our time is of great importance, thanks to its new possibilities. The introduction of new information and communication technology expands access to education, forming an open education system, and changes the idea of the qualifications needed by modern graduate students [1]. The most significant group of benefits is teaching the virtues of computer-based training. For example, teachers use the ability of computers to react instantly to input information to create simple training programs in the form of exercises. The technical advantage of teaching English with the help of multimedia technology is that sound cards allow users to record their speech and then compare it with the pronunciation of native speakers. Graphics capabilities of computers can represent any type of activity in the form of pictures or animation. This is particularly important when learning new vocabulary, as images on the monitor allow students to associate English phrases directly with actions, rather than with phrases in their native language. Moreover, the media are an excellent means of interactive communication between different linguistic groups, which is particularly evident in the application of computer networks. This could be a local area network connecting several machines in one class, or the Internet — a global network of millions of users [2]. These advantages allow us to conclude that multimedia learning has great potential for teaching oral speech in other languages. Through the optimal combination of a number technology (language laboratory, video, television, radio, newspapers, magazines, books, bibliographies, and phones) and having additional features (interactivity, graphics capabilities,

etc.), multimedia learning provides almost limitless opportunities for teaching and learning. In recent years, there has been a tendency in the education system to change the learning paradigm, such that schools are transitioning from transfer of knowledge to students in finished form toward the organization and management of self-learning and cognitive activity. With today's requirements for education, where a major element is independent work by students, high schools can enhance the process of learning, teaching methods, and forms of work organization that will develop the ability to learn, find needed information using a variety of information sources, and students' cognitive independence [7].

Modern pedagogical science seeks to use new technology in teaching. The aforementioned interactive media get their proper use. Most of the wide variety of interactive educational software for learning English is aimed at independent elaboration of phonetic and grammatical aspects and making their use automatic. Features of these programs include interactive dialogues, speech recognition and visualization of pronunciation, animated videos showing articulation of sounds, exercises for development of all kinds of speech skills, videos with translation, and tracking one's own learning outcomes. Since the purpose of learning the English language is communicative activity, which requires practical command of the language, the task of teachers is to revitalize all students in the learning process to create a context for their creative activity. The use of modern means, such as awareness programs and Internet technology, as well as cooperative learning and project methodology, allow us to solve these problems [9]. So, Internet sources that may come to the aid of foreign language teachers in the organization of independent work, include broadcasting, interacting with and searching in online resources, where cognitive information, training materials and conditions can be found that are conducive to the formation of professional competence for future specialists [3]. Today we have a unique helper that allows us to bring in the best teachers from many countries through the software they create. Intensification of the process of transition to an information society, associated with the widespread introduction of new information technology and computer telecommunications, necessitates the development of other forms and methods of teaching foreign languages. Along with the use of traditional technology learning, opportunities for new information technology can help teachers in the selection of more interesting and varied educational materials to carry out a differentiated approach for each student, and thereby contribute to better assimilation of necessary knowledge and skills. Among the various types of innovation, as shown by the results of a survey conducted in the universities of the CIS, teachers are most familiar with training through the use of multimedia tools (66.7 %) [6].

Multimedia technology is considered to be information technology training that integrates audiovisual information in several media (text, video, audio, graphics, animation, etc.) [4]. The use of multimedia technology in the learning process allows for improvements in the process of organic combination of traditional and innovative forms and methods of education; implementation of training, information, games, modeling, design and analysis functions; performance of such general didactic principles as visibility and accessibility; feasibility of systematic transition from education to self-education; a positive emotional background for training; and linking theory to practice [5]. In addition, multimedia technology is supported by multimedia programs, encyclopedias, dictionaries, and a special information educational environment created for holistic knowledge of the world in the context of computer-aided design and modeling. Multimedia technology acts as a special intellectual activity, which means it has a number of advantages compared with other information technology training:

1. The pedagogy means continuous improvement of content and methods of education in modern conditions.
2. Provides opportunities to identify and support students with linguistic abilities.
3. Represents the basis of distance learning.

4. Provides access to best practices in education and training of the general public through the educational world of the Internet and an extensive communication network.

5. Creates an artificial language environment, allowing the study of foreign languages (FL) at students' own pace, increasing the independence and responsibility of students when organizing FL training for all age groups, and allows students to enter into training in the intercultural component of FL.

6. Multimedia technology is new and apparently has limitless possibilities for creation of means of graphic clarity.

Multimedia (computer with additional devices) can be a powerful tool for everyone to learn foreign languages through self-study, and allow close monitoring and ongoing operational support [3].

Along with positive aspects, there are some negative trends affecting the mass creation and implementation of multimedia technology in the learning process. These include:

1. Lack of ability of existing education systems to make active use of multimedia technology, and to integrate it into the educational process and its organization;

2. Lack of a developed methodology of multimedia technology;

3. Lack of financial resources for the creation and widespread adoption of multimedia technology;

4. The device is not designed evaluation.

In order to introduce multimedia technology in the learning process, it is first necessary to create conditions for sound pedagogical and methodological application of multimedia technology. The integration of the Internet in education and, in particular, its use in the teaching of foreign languages, is now quite relevant. The combination of traditional and newer teaching methods of language teaching will ensure a higher level of learning. Unfortunately at the present time, the use of multimedia technology to intensify individual work in the study of foreign languages is largely constrained by the high cost of computer equipment, as well as the lack of a sufficient number of theoretically grounded and experimentally tested computer programs intended for independent foreign language learning.

In general, a situation currently exists in which, on the one hand, there are a small number of theoretical studies that have not been widely put into practice; and on the other, and there are many disparate programs that do not have a serious theoretical basis [8]. The current analysis showed that in pedagogical science, especially in the practice of domestic university teaching, the capabilities of learning software, including multimedia technology, are underestimated. This is due primarily to complexity and insufficient development of a theory of the concept of multimedia technology as a didactic tool.

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